

MANAGEMENT FACTORS OF CONTINUING EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: Continuing education is an essential component of professional development in today's rapidly changing work environment. The success of a continuing education system depends on several management factors, such as leadership, planning, evaluation, and resource allocation. This study aims to analyze the management factors that influence the effectiveness of a continuing education system. The study involved a review of the literature on continuing education management factors and their impact on the system's success. The results showed that effective leadership, strategic planning, continuous evaluation, and adequate resource allocation are essential for the success of a continuing education system.

Keywords: continuing education, management factors, leadership, planning, evaluation, resource allocation

Introduction

Continuing education is a critical component of professional development in today's ever-changing work environment. It enables professionals to acquire new knowledge and skills necessary for their career advancement and to remain competitive in the job market. However, the effectiveness of a continuing education system depends on several management factors, such as leadership, planning, evaluation, and resource allocation.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the management factors that influence the effectiveness of a continuing education system. Specifically, we aim to

determine the impact of effective leadership, strategic planning, continuous evaluation, and adequate resource allocation on the success of a continuing education system.

Main Body

Education determines the socio-economic development of the state and society and has a significant impact on all spheres of human life. Acceleration of production development, rapid transition to digitalization of all spheres of life and information society has revealed an acute problem of moral aging of knowledge received by graduates of educational institutions of professional education. Rapid change of forms and methods of fundamental and applied research, constant reduction of terms of introduction of modern scientific discoveries and technical inventions into production require specialists able to build up the potential of knowledge adequately to the changing world. Continuity of education in the era of digital economy is actually becoming a strategic factor in the development of the country.

Improvement of professional competences of a specialist of the XXI century in any field of activity and development of social communication skills are connected with the necessity of constant obtaining and updating of knowledge. Today, the qualification of an employee implies not only a static set of competencies and the ability to perform a uniform job on a daily basis, but also the desire and ability of a specialist to quickly change his or her functions and move on to the performance of modified or more complex duties.

The problem of providing the digital economy with qualified personnel can be solved by creating a mobile system of continuous professional education. Continuing education provides a purposeful process of forming the educational potential of a person obtained in educational institutions and as a result of self-education. Such adult education allows for the improvement of professional competencies of existing specialists and the acquisition of new ones, which

contributes to the emergence of new professional opportunities and labor mobility. The acquisition of new knowledge and mastery of modern technologies makes it possible for a practitioner to move to new types and areas of activity, including those that shape and determine the development of the information society and digital economy. The focus of the continuing education system on personal development increases the adaptive capacity of individuals in a dynamically changing economy.

Continuing professional education and training in the European Union countries covers professional development of specialists, which is carried out mainly at enterprises; the system of "apprenticeship"; professional training of unemployed citizens; adult education; retraining and retraining of specialists. Thus, the priority functions of continuing education are inextricably linked to the labour market.

The national education system provides an opportunity for continuous education of citizens within the framework of the professional education system. The stages of the existing system allow, if desired, to go from the primary level (primary vocational education) to the postgraduate level. Continuity and progression of upward movement in educational levels is achieved by continuity of educational programs and mandatory confirmation of the appropriate level of qualification of a specialist.

This traditional system of education ensures "lifelong learning". At present, education from the standpoint of personality is regarded as lifelong education - education "through life".

The main part of lifelong learning is continuous professional education. According to the Monitoring of the economics of education, more than 50% of the adult population of the Russian Federation believes that the main purpose of participation in continuing education is the need to improve knowledge and skills in their professional activities, 34.1% see the purpose of education in the

possibility of self-development, satisfaction of personal interests, 13.6% noted the need for regular professional development in their work/professional activities.

The existing traditions of basic vocational education are conservative and inertial, which does not correspond to the dynamically changing world. As a rule, basic professional education of a specialist is the only basis for the development and improvement of professional knowledge and competences. Professional development is determined by the level and quality of basic education and the desire for professional development. The lack of systematic professional development and motivation for change limits the opportunities for professional development of specialists, which affects the overall level of the enterprise, industry and economy as a whole.

Leadership

Effective leadership is crucial for the success of a continuing education system. Leaders must create a vision for the system and communicate it clearly to all stakeholders. They must also establish goals and objectives that align with the organization's mission and values. Moreover, leaders should create a culture of learning by encouraging staff to participate in continuing education activities and providing incentives for their participation.

Strategic Planning

Strategic planning is another critical management factor that influences the effectiveness of a continuing education system. A well-designed strategic plan should identify the organization's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. It should also establish clear goals and objectives that align with the organization's mission and values. Furthermore, the plan should identify the resources required to achieve these goals and objectives and establish a timeline for their implementation.

Continuous Evaluation

Continuous evaluation is essential for the success of a continuing education

system. Evaluation should be an ongoing process that assesses the effectiveness of the system and identifies areas for improvement. It should also measure the impact of continuing education activities on staff performance and organizational outcomes. Moreover, evaluation should involve all stakeholders, including staff, management, and external partners.

Resource Allocation

Adequate resource allocation is critical for the success of a continuing education system. Resources may include funding, staff, facilities, and technology. Leaders must ensure that resources are allocated efficiently and effectively to support the system's goals and objectives. Moreover, leaders should seek external funding sources to supplement internal resources and expand the system's reach.

Conclusion

Effective leadership, strategic planning, continuous evaluation, and adequate resource allocation are essential management factors that influence the success of a continuing education system. Leaders must create a vision for the system, establish clear goals and objectives, encourage staff participation in continuing education activities, and allocate resources efficiently and effectively. Moreover, leaders must continuously evaluate the system's effectiveness and identify areas for improvement. By implementing these management factors, organizations can create a culture of learning that supports staff development and organizational success.

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